

1 **CDKN2A and CDKN2B are silenced during resistance to chemotherapy *in vitro*.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7
8 We describe here silencing of *CDKN2A* and *CDKN2B* during resistance to chemotherapy *in vitro*.

9 Citations

10 1. Monzon, J., Liu, L., Brill, H., Goldstein, A.M., Tucker, M.A., From, L., McLaughlin, J., Hogg, D. and
11 Lassam, N.J., 1998. CDKN2A mutations in multiple primary melanomas. New England Journal of
12 Medicine, 338(13), pp.879-887.

13 2. Wrensch, M., Jenkins, R.B., Chang, J.S., Yeh, R.F., Xiao, Y., Decker, P.A., Ballman, K.V., Berger,
14 M., Buckner, J.C., Chang, S. and Giannini, C., 2009. Variants in the CDKN2B and RTEL1 regions are
15 associated with high-grade glioma susceptibility. Nature genetics, 41(8), pp.905-908.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28